

EVALUATION OF CEREBROSPINAL FLUID VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR LEVELS DURING THE DIAGNOSTIC PHASE IN PATIENTS WITH MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

Keywords

Multiple Sclerosis,

Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor,

Blood–Brain Barrier

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ABSTRACT

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is a chronic immune-mediated demyelinating disorder of the central nervous system and represents a leading cause of non-traumatic neurological disability in young adults. Its pathophysiology is characterized by a complex interplay between inflammatory mechanisms and neurodegenerative processes, with blood–brain barrier (BBB) disruption serving as a pivotal event in lesion development. Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF), a potent mediator of angiogenesis and vascular permeability, has emerged as a molecule of interest due to its regulatory effects on inflammatory cell trafficking and BBB integrity. This study aimed to evaluate cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) VEGF-A levels in 40 newly diagnosed patients with Relapsing–Remitting MS (RRMS) followed at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Medicine. CSF samples obtained from individuals undergoing lumbar puncture with a preliminary diagnosis of intracranial hypertension were included as the control group. In conclusion, CSF VEGF levels were significantly higher in the MS group compared to controls. However, no statistically significant correlation was observed between VEGF concentrations and IgG index, number of lesion localization areas, or presence of gadolinium contrast-enhanced lesions in the MS group. These findings suggest that VEGF may serve as a potential disease onset biomarker in MS. Further elucidation of VEGF-mediated mechanisms may enhance our understanding of MS pathogenesis and inform the development of targeted therapeutic strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is a chronic, inflammatory, demyelinating disease of the central nervous system (CNS). By predominantly affecting young adults and representing the second most common cause of non-traumatic disability in this age group, it constitutes a major global health concern. It is currently estimated to affect approximately 2.8 million individuals worldwide. A clear female predominance has been reported, with a female-to-male ratio of 2–3:1 or even higher. MS is clinically classified into distinct subtypes: Relapsing–Remitting MS (RRMS), the most common form characterized by acute relapses followed by remission; Secondary Progressive MS (SPMS), which typically evolves from RRMS in the absence of effective treatment; and Primary Progressive MS (PPMS), accounting for approximately 10% of cases and characterized by continuous disease progression without remission over a period of at least one year^{1,2}.

Although demyelination represents the primary pathological hallmark of MS, the disease is also characterized by axonal degeneration, astroglial scarring, and multiple additional structural alterations^{3–5}. Both adaptive immune cells (including T and B lymphocytes) and innate immune components (such as monocytes, microglia, lymphocytes, and natural killer cells) contribute to disease pathophysiology. The frequent perivascular localization of MS lesions and the critical role of altered vascular permeability in lesion development highlight the importance of vascular mechanisms in MS^{6,7}. However, the molecular pathways underlying the vascular alterations observed in MS remain incompletely elucidated^{8,9}. In recent years, Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) has emerged as a molecule of interest, with accumulating evidence suggesting a significant role in MS pathophysiology^{10,11}.

Volume: 4

Issue: 2

Page: 188–195

Received: 04.03.2026

Accepted: 10.05.2026

Available online: 30.06.2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20809913

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VEGF is a heparin-binding dimeric glycoprotein that induces endothelial cell proliferation and migration, thereby promoting angiogenesis¹². Beyond its angiogenic function, VEGF increases vascular permeability, facilitating the extravasation of plasma macromolecules and immune cells such as monocytes and macrophages¹³. Through these mechanisms, it may amplify inflammatory processes. These properties partly explain its pathological relevance in inflammatory and autoimmune disorders, including systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, and MS¹⁴.

Disruption of the blood–brain barrier (BBB) is considered a fundamental event in both the initiation and progression of MS. Experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) models have demonstrated increased BBB permeability prior to the development of histological lesions, and the distribution of inflammatory infiltrates has been shown to overlap with areas of maximal BBB disruption^{15,16}. BBB dysfunction may exacerbate neuroinflammatory processes by facilitating the entry of blood-derived immune mediators into the brain parenchyma and allowing myelin basic protein degradation products to enter systemic circulation^{17,18}.

Studies investigating the association between MS and VEGF have yielded noteworthy findings, including elevated serum VEGF levels correlated with spinal demyelinating plaque length, VEGF overexpression in EAE and MS models, and upregulation of VEGFR-1 in normal-appearing white matter in postmortem MS brains^{19,20}. Chronic VEGF overexpression in reactive or gliotic astrocytes has been proposed as a key mechanism contributing to BBB disruption. Structural alterations observed in capillary endothelial cells during EAE are consistent with the known effects of VEGF on endothelial morphology^{3,4}. Furthermore, VEGF has been shown to enhance inflammatory immune responses by promoting Th1 cell polarization²¹. The observation that anti-VEGF therapies can attenuate inflammation in experimental models further supports its potential as a therapeutic target²².

Given that cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) directly reflects pathological processes within the CNS and plays a critical role in its nourishment, protection, and functional regulation, the evaluation of VEGF levels in CSF may provide valuable insight into MS pathogenesis. Accordingly, this study aimed to compare CSF VEGF-A levels between patients diagnosed with RRMS in remission and a control group without MS, and to investigate the relationship between VEGF levels and

laboratory as well as radiological findings within the MS cohort. The data obtained are expected to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the role of VEGF in MS pathophysiology and to inform the development of future VEGF-targeted therapeutic strategies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Participants

This study was approved by the Cumhuriyet University Clinical Research Ethics Committee (Decision No: 2024-03/04, dated 26.03.2024). The project was supported by the Cumhuriyet University Scientific Research Projects Commission under grant number T-2024-1057 (Medical Specialty Research Project).

Participants were recruited between April 2024 and May 2025 from patients followed at the Neurology Outpatient Clinic of Sivas Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Medicine. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to inclusion.

The study population consisted of 80 individuals, including 40 patients in remission at the time of diagnosis with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and 40 individuals without MS serving as the control group.

Patient Group

The patient group comprised newly diagnosed MS patients in remission. Exclusion criteria included the presence of chronic inflammatory diseases, history of malignancy, chronic medication use, and chronic alcohol consumption.

Lumbar puncture (LP) in MS patients was performed prior to the initiation of acute relapse treatment (e.g., methylprednisolone or plasmapheresis) and before the commencement of any disease-modifying therapy. Additionally, a minimum interval of four weeks between the last clinical symptoms and LP was ensured. All patients were subsequently diagnosed according to the 2017 McDonald criteria and were classified as Relapsing–Remitting MS (RRMS).

Control Group

The control group consisted of individuals who initially underwent lumbar puncture with a preliminary diagnosis of

idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH), but in whom IIH was subsequently excluded. Inclusion criteria for controls were:

Normal cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) opening pressure (70–190 mmH₂O),

Absence of pathological findings in CSF biochemistry, cytology, microbiology, and infectious panels,

No radiological evidence supporting IIH.

Individuals with abnormal CSF findings in any of these parameters were excluded.

Lumbar Puncture Procedure

All lumbar punctures in both groups were performed in the lateral decubitus position, with hip and knee flexion, avoiding excessive neck flexion. No sedation was administered before or during the procedure. CSF samples were obtained at first needle entry.

Clinical and Radiological Data Collection

Demographic characteristics (age and sex) and CSF VEGF-A levels were recorded for both groups.

In the MS group, additional data including IgG index, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) findings were documented.

All patients in the MS cohort were classified as RRMS. VEGF-A levels were analyzed according to:

IgG index,

MRI lesion areas burden (number of affected regions ≤ 2 vs. >2).

Subgroup analyses were additionally performed based on:

MRI lesion localization (periventricular, cortical/juxtacortical, infratentorial, spinal cord),

Presence of contrast enhancement.

Cranial and spinal MRI scans were performed using the same imaging device and independently evaluated by one specialist radiologist and one neurologist to determine lesion presence and lesion count.

Biochemical and Hematological Assessment

Peripheral blood samples were collected at the time of lumbar puncture for routine laboratory analysis.

For VEGF-A measurement, CSF samples were centrifuged and stored at -80°C until analysis. CSF samples were also sent

for routine examination, including cell count, glucose, protein concentration, and serological testing.

For biochemical analyses:

Serum samples were collected in dry tubes.

CSF samples were collected in plain tubes.

Serum and CSF biochemical analyses were performed using the Beckman Coulter AU5800 automated analyzer (Beckman Coulter Inc., Brea, Florida) with the manufacturer's kits, employing a fully automated nephelometric method.

CSF VEGF-A concentrations were measured using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit (Reed Biotech, Catalog No: RE1061H), following the manufacturer's protocol. The assay characteristics were as follows:

Sensitivity: 18.75 pg/mL

Measurement range: 31.25–2000 pg/mL

Coefficient of variation: $<10\%$

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 23.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

Data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test along with visual inspection methods (histograms and Q–Q plots). Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data, and as median (25th–75th percentile) with minimum–maximum values for non-normally distributed data. Categorical variables were expressed as number and percentage [n (%)].

Comparisons of categorical variables between groups were performed using the Pearson chi-square test with Monte Carlo simulation. For comparisons of continuous variables between two independent groups, the Independent Samples t-test with bootstrap method was used for normally distributed data, while the Mann–Whitney U test with Monte Carlo simulation was applied for non-normally distributed data.

The diagnostic performance of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) VEGF-A levels was evaluated using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. The area under the curve (AUC), sensitivity, and specificity values were calculated and reported.

All statistical tests were two-tailed, and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 80 participants were included in the study, comprising 40 patients (50%) and 40 controls (50%). The majority of participants were female (83.8%), while males accounted for 16.3% of the cohort.

In the MS group, oligoclonal band (OCB) positivity was observed in 61.54% of the 40 patients for whom OCB data were available.

Contrast enhancement within central nervous system lesions was detected in 17.5% of patients.

Regarding lesion distribution, periventricular and cortical/juxtacortical involvement was present in 82.5% of cases. Infratentorial lesions were observed in 57.5% of patients, and spinal cord involvement was identified in 20%.

Descriptive statistics for the sociodemographic, clinical, and radiological characteristics of the study groups are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Sociodemographic, Clinical, and Radiological Characteristics of the Study Groups

		N	%
Groups	Control	40	%50.0
	Patient	40	%50.0
Gender	Female	67	%83.8
	Male	13	%16.3
IgG Index	<0.70	20	%50.0
	>0.70	20	%50.0
Oligoclonal Band Type 2 Positivity	-	16	%40.0
	+	24	%60.0
Contrast Enhancement Lesion		7	%17.5
Non-Contrast Enhancement Lesion		36	%90.0
Lesion Localization			
Periventricular Lesion Involvement		33	%82.5
Cortical/Juxtacortical Lesion Involvement		33	%82.5
Infratentorial Lesion Involvement		23	%57.5
Spinal Cord Lesion Involvement		8	%20.0
Lesion Region Count	≤2	17	%42.5
	>2	23	%57.5

No statistically significant difference was observed between the groups in terms of sex distribution ($p = 0.225$). The mean age of all participants was 30.9 ± 8.0 years, and the mean cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) VEGF-A level was 64.6 ± 20.6 pg/mL. When age was analyzed between the two groups, no

significant difference was detected ($p = 0.065$). However, CSF VEGF-A levels were significantly higher in the patient group compared to the control group ($p = 0.001$). This finding suggests a potential association between MS and elevated CSF VEGF-A levels (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison of Sex Distribution, Age, and CSF VEGF-A Levels Between the Patient and Control Groups

	Groups		P
	Control (n=40)	Patient (n=40)	
Gender, n (%)			0.225
Female	36 (90.0)	31 (77.5)	
Male	4 (10.0)	9 (22.5)	
Age (Year), Median (Q1-Q3)	32,52 ±7,73	29,22±7,73	0,065
BOS VEGF-A Levels, Mean ± SD.	54.8 2± 11.4	74.31 ± 23.0	0.001 [†]

[†] Independent Samples t test

The performance of CSF VEGF-A levels in discriminating the patient group from the control group was statistically significant (AUC = 0.793, SE = 0.054, p < 0.001). The area under the ROC curve (AUC) indicated good discriminatory

ability. At the determined cut-off value of >62.69 pg/mL, the sensitivity was 77.5% and the specificity was 80%. These findings demonstrate that CSF VEGF-A levels exhibit high diagnostic accuracy in distinguishing MS patients from controls (Figure 1).

CSF: cerebrospinal fluid, VEGF-A: vascular endothelial growth factor A, AUC: area under the curve, SE: standard error, p: statistical significance, Cut-off: threshold value, Sensitivity, Specificity.

Figure 1. ROC Analysis of CSF VEGF-A Levels and Their Distribution Across Groups

No statistically significant differences were observed when CSF VEGF-A levels were compared across categorical variables, including IgG index, contrast enhancement, and lesion localization ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons). Similarly, no

significant difference was detected in terms of lesion region count, localization and Gadolinium enhancement on radiological imaging ($p = 0.061$). The comparison of CSF VEGF-A levels according to categorical laboratory and radiological characteristics is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of CSF VEGF-A Levels According to Categorical Laboratory and Radiological Characteristics

	n	CSF VEGF-A Levels Mean±SD or Median (Q1-Q3)	P
IgG Index			0.912 ^t
<0.70	20	74.72± 23.49	
>0.70	20	73.90 ± 23.14	
Contrast Enhancement			0.828 ^t
no	33	74.68 ± 7.23	
yes	7	72.56 ± 24.0	
Periventricular Lesion Involvement			0.389 ^t
no	7	78.9 ± 12.1	
yes	33	73.3 ± 24.8	
Cortical/Juxtacortical Lesion Involvement			0.936 ^t
no	7	73.94 ± 13.46	
yes	33	74.38 ± 24.73	
Infratentorial Lesion Involvement			0.141 ^u
no	17	72.6 (67.6-87.4)	
yes	23	71.3 (47.9-83.7)	
Cervical Spinal Cord Lesion Involvement			0.956 ^t
no	32	74.31 ± 20.79	
yes	8	74.72 ± 32.31	
-	18	71,39± 19,37	
Lesion Region Count			0.084 ^u
≤2	17	82.87 (65.16-129.33)	
>2	23	67.33 (21.97-108.34)	

The correlation coefficients between CSF VEGF-A levels and IgG index, lesion count, and number of involved regions were weak and not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, CSF VEGF-A levels were found to be significantly higher in patients with MS compared to controls ($p = 0.001$). This finding supports the hypothesis that VEGF may be involved in early immune and inflammatory processes within the central nervous system (CNS) during the initial phases of MS. However, no significant correlation was found between CSF VEGF-A levels and intrathecal immune activation markers such as the IgG index, oligoclonal band positivity, and radiological parameters ($p > 0.05$). These findings

suggest that VEGF may be a potential biomarker indicating early pathophysiological processes.

Previous studies have investigated VEGF in a broad spectrum of conditions, including malignancies, retinal and macular degenerative disorders, cerebrovascular diseases, and neurodegenerative conditions. Similar to oncological strategies that target angiogenesis to limit tumor progression, growing evidence highlights the potential relevance of anti-VEGF approaches in neurological diseases, particularly through modulation of blood-brain barrier (BBB) integrity and

inflammatory responses^{23–27}. Studies examining serum VEGF levels in MS patients have consistently reported elevated levels compared to healthy controls, with more pronounced increases during active disease phases and relatively lower levels during remission^{13,19,28,29}. Under inflammatory and hypoxic conditions, leukocytes, monocytes/macrophages, and endothelial cells in the peripheral circulation contribute to VEGF production, further supporting its role in immune-mediated processes^{12,13}. Clinical correlation studies have generally demonstrated positive associations between serum VEGF levels and disease activity or severity. Harandi et al. reported that patients with higher baseline VEGF levels experienced shorter relapse-free intervals, suggesting a potential prognostic value²⁹. Similarly, Su et al. demonstrated an association between serum VEGF levels and spinal cord lesion length, and a positive correlation between serum VEGF levels and EDSS scores was also observed. Although in our study we used only CSF instead of serum VEGF levels, our findings similarly indicate a lack of association between VEGF levels and brain lesion burden¹⁹. This may suggest that CSF VEGF-A elevation reflects early neurovascular or inflammatory signaling rather than cumulative structural damage detectable on MRI. The absence of correlation with radiological parameters further supports the possibility that VEGF acts upstream in the disease cascade. Taken together, our findings reinforce the concept that VEGF may function as a biomarker of early CNS inflammatory activity in MS. However, its relationship with disease progression, lesion evolution, and clinical disability warrants further investigation in larger, longitudinal studies.

When previous studies evaluating CSF VEGF-A levels in MS are examined, heterogeneous findings are evident. Tham et al. demonstrated decreased VEGF-A mRNA expression in CSF mononuclear cells of MS patients. This reduction may be explained by the suppressive effects of proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF and IFN- γ on VEGF-A transcription, or by compensatory regulatory mechanisms aimed at limiting the potential proinflammatory or neurotoxic properties of VEGF-A. Additionally, alterations in CSF monocyte proportions and/or monocyte phenotypes may modulate the VEGF signaling axis and contribute to these findings. Consistently, Seabrook et al. reported decreased soluble VEGF-A protein levels during relapse in experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) models, along with reduced neuronal VEGF expression on immunohistochemical analysis. These observations are in contrast to our findings. Iacobaeus et al. reported declining

VEGF levels over the disease course and, in line with our study, did not identify significant associations between VEGF levels and radiological parameters^{30–32}. Conversely, Talbot et al. demonstrated elevated CSF VEGF levels in patients with RRMS, consistent with our results. In their study, as in ours, no significant correlations were observed between VEGF levels and IgG index or MRI parameters³³. Furthermore, another investigation reported persistent upregulation of VEGF in MS plaques and EAE lesions. Notably, administration of exogenous VEGF to rats immunized with myelin basic protein induced inflammatory responses, supporting a potential pathogenic role of VEGF in demyelinating disease³⁴.

Our study has several limitations. First, it was conducted at a single center with a relatively limited sample size. Second, serum VEGF levels were not assessed, preventing comparison between systemic and intrathecal VEGF dynamics. Third, the inclusion of only newly diagnosed patients precluded longitudinal or prognostic evaluation.

In conclusion, VEGF-A appears to influence blood–brain barrier integrity and inflammatory processes in MS independently of conventional MRI characteristics and established CSF inflammatory markers. Modulation of the VEGF pathway may therefore represent a novel therapeutic strategy in MS and other neuroinflammatory disorders. Large-scale, multicenter, and longitudinal studies are required to further clarify the mechanistic and clinical significance of VEGF signaling in MS.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

There are no potential conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgements

No

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